

WAYS TO INCREASE PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE TEACHERS

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Annotation

This article provides theoretical knowledge about the professional competence and competence of prospective teachers, and reveals new ways to improve the professional competence of teachers.

Keywords: competence, competence, teacher identity, professional competence, professional competence, method, methodology, development

МЕТОДЫ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОЙ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ БУДУЩИХ ПЕДАГОГОВ

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Аннотация

В данной статье даны теоретические знания о профессиональной компетентности и компетентности будущих педагогов, раскрыты новые способы повышения профессиональной компетентности педагогов.

Ключевые слова: компетентность, компетентность, личность учителя, профессиональная компетентность, профессиональная компетентность, метод, методика, развитие

Improving the quality of education is one of the most urgent problems of the world community today. In order to solve it, it is necessary to modernize the

content of education, to review the technologies of the educational process and the ultimate goal of education. Education can be considered as a specially organized process of developing the ability to independently solve problems of personal and social importance in various spheres of activity. Such an understanding of the purpose of education, in turn, creates a basis for the realization of a competent approach.

A competent approach to education is a relatively new phenomenon for the pedagogy of our country. Its development is related to the fact that in the modern stage of modernization of education in our Independent Republic, first of all, its purpose changes radically. "Competence" and "competence" are the main concepts of the competent approach in education. The analysis of the sources shows that they are complex, multi-component and interdisciplinary concepts that do not have a single value definition in the scientific literature.

According to researchers, they differ in size, category, semantics and logical structure and can be considered as a description of a competent person (characteristics, habits, etc.). A description of a competent person (trait, quality of a person, its component), integrated education in the structure of a person, a system of personal characteristics, conditions arising as a result of the acquisition of knowledge, skills and qualifications (readiness, orientation, etc.), can be expressed as is often equated with competent knowledge and experience. Today, the terms "competence" and "competence" are widely used and stabilized in pedagogical literature. But until now, there is no single and clear definition of the concept of "competence" that can be applied to the optimal image of a graduate of this or that stage of education.

In the sources, the terms "competence" and "competence" are used to express qualities such as knowledge, skills, qualifications, abilities, diligence, and professional skills of a person. We use the term "competence" in this work. "Competentia" is a Latin word whose dictionary meaning in Uzbek means "a

person who knows well", "having experience". Therefore, a person who is competent in a certain field is considered to have the appropriate knowledge and ability to think reasonably about this field and to carry out effective activities in it. The following definitions of competence and competence can be found in scientific sources: motivated ability; characteristics and qualities of a person, personal line; activity readiness criteria; ability to solve the problem and obtain its results; activity-related knowledge, competence, skills and experience (solving a problem mastered by a person, combining methods and ways into a whole), at the same time, the motivated and emotional sphere of a person A.A. Verbitsky and M.D. Ilyazova defined these concepts as follows:

competence is a system of goals, values, motives, personal qualities, knowledge, skills, skills, abilities and experiences that ensure the implementation of this or that activity by a person; and competence is the competence of a person, manifested in practice, characterized by the level of acquisition of practical activity technologies and the development of social and moral qualities of a person.

A.S. Belkin and V.V. The Nesterovs defined competence as a set of professional authority and functions that create the necessary conditions for effective activity in the educational process, and competence as a set of professional and personal qualities that ensure the effective implementation of competence.

V.N. According to Vvedensky, competence is a kind of personal description, and competence is a set of specific professional or functional characteristics. M.A. Kholodnaya defined competence as follows:

Competence is a special type of organization of subject-specific knowledge that allows making effective decisions in appropriate activities. G.K. Selevko understood competence as a form of a complex of knowledge, skills and abilities that allows to set a goal for environmental change and achieve it.

Competence is an integrated quality based on the knowledge and experiences acquired by a person in the process of education and socialization and directed to independent and successful participation in activities, manifested in his general abilities and readiness in his activities.

The presence of such pedagogical skills in future teachers helps to increase the quality and effectiveness of education.

References

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